

Research Article

Assessment of household food handling knowledge and practice changes before and after the Covid19 pandemic

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Abstract:

Present study aims Assessment of household food handling knowledge and practice changes before and after the Covid19 pandemic. At Present SARS-CoV-2 has not been shown to be transmitted by food. However, the COVID-19 epidemic has altered household's perceptions about food and safety. This study evaluated households food safety behaviours before and after the COVID-19 pandemic using cross-sectional survey. In our study, the most significant difference was observed in kitchen and food hygiene in terms of sanitization for infection prevention. The expenditure on the hygiene was increased fivefold. We selected higher levels of observed data to summarize Table 2. Hand hygiene and proper hand washing knowledge in participants before Covid19 was in the category "No knowledge" with 196 (71.27%), but Secure knowledge was 210 (73.36%) after Covid19. The importance of cleaning groceries in participants before Covid19 was Primary 156 (56.72%), while Secure knowledge 167 (56.72%) after Covid19 was noted. Food securities Knowledge in participants before the Covid19 was Primary 93(33.18%) whereas secure knowledge 179(65.09%), Also, before Covid19, primary hygiene when handling cooking utensils was 197 (71.63%), while secure knowledge was 213 (77.45%). As a result, a questionnaire was used to collect information on household expenses, such as knowledge of food security, hand hygiene and proper hand washing, the usage of hand sanitizer, and hygiene when using kitchen utensils before and after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Covid-19, hygiene, food safety, households, pandemic.

Introduction

Coronavirus illness (COVID-19) is caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) and has been marked a worldwide public health emergency by the World Health Organization (WHO), leading in a disastrous global pandemic [1,2]. In November 2019, the first COVID-19 patient was diagnosed in Wuhan province, China, with severe pneumonia. [3]. The symptoms of COVID-19 appear after a period of incubation of about 5 days [4]. With fever, cough and fatigue as the common symptoms [2].

It has been estimated that the economic impact of the disease globally to individuals, households, health systems and governments is between USD1-2.7 trillion [5].

The decrease in household expenditure for some of the food and non-food goods such as education, water, power, clothes and apparel seen in this Nigerian study might be related to self-isolation and quarantine rules in effect during lockdown. (Yap, 2020). We expected expenditure on education to rise during the lockdown, but there was minimal home schooling because of a lack of suitable educational platforms. On the other hand, expenditure on household items such as toiletries, hand sanitizers, face masks, hand gloves, disinfectants, and entertainment increased. This could be due to a relatively high level of usage of the items in order to prevent the spread of COVID-19 and increased prices during the pandemic [6], however, these were not statistically significant.

According to Haque and colleagues, there was an increased utilization and price increase for items such as antibiotics, analgesics, vitamins and personal protective equipment in Bangladesh [7].

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), five main aspects to safer food include keeping it clean, separating raw and cooked food, cooking thoroughly, storing food at safe temperatures, and using safe water and raw materials [8]. This is to ensure the presentation of safer food, optimal health and

prevention of foodborne illnesses. Foodborne illness affects 1 out of every 10 people worldwide [9].

A possible cause of foodborne illness is food contamination which can result from poor food safety knowledge and practice of food handlers in the home, which is the main location for foodborne illness outbreak Byrd-Bredbenner et al. [10] Both Ehuwa, Jaiswal and Jaiswal [11] and Preneuf and Morales [12] reported that at least 10% – 20% of foodborne illness outbreaks were due to contamination by the food handlers. There are limited studies that provide insights into the association between the status of food security and home food safety among households [13-16].

The study focused on understanding the practices of food handlers in households. Assessed the impact of covid19 on strategies to improve individuals' knowledge on food safety and proper food hygiene.

Jagdalpur is a city in the tribal district of Bastar in Chhattisgarh, a state in central India. On the banks of the Indravati River, ornate Bastar Palace was built by the region's former kings. The nearby Anthropological Museum displays tribal artifacts. West of the city, Chitrakote Falls cascades over broad cliffs. To the southeast, tigers roam through teak and bamboo forests at Kanger Valley National Park.

Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted between December 2022 and June 2023. 275 households took part in this survey. This survey conducted in rural municipalities of Jagdalpur, Chhattisgarh, India. The participants were recruited from a list of students that are currently living in Jagdalpur in district of Bastar, Chhattisgarh, India.

Data collection

Participants were sampled based on age, gender, ethnicity, and study program to obtain comprehensive data. The study includes interaction with participants, guided by

questions based on current research results. This corresponds to a sample size of 350 households with a confidence interval of 95 and a confidence level of 5. 75 out of 350 households were eliminated for not willing to participate in the study. The study included families that provided written informed consent, as well as any family members infected with Covid19 during the epidemic. Those who did not complete the questionnaire after three visits, as well as any family members who were not infected with Covid19 throughout the pandemic, also the participant's age above 55 were excluded from the study. Six research assistants were trained on the questionnaire's content and interview methodology. Following the interview, the questionnaires were reviewed for completeness. Finally, 275 women consented to participate in the study. The participants' inclusion criteria were defined as women, and were responsible for food handling in their households. The research assistants followed the sampling procedure by visiting selected houses and interviewing the individual responsible for the household's food preparation.

Data Analysis:

The questionnaire data were coded and entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and imported to statistical Software. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

Ethical considerations

Before participating in the study, all participants provided informed consent and were advised that their responses would be kept anonymous and confidential. The study was conducted per the Declaration of Helsinki, and the protocol was approved by Shri Balaji Institute of Medical Science, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India Research Ethics Committee (SBMSCG/RIC/22439)

Results

Two hundred seventy five (Female households) one from each family across the different regions of Jagdalpur have participated in this study (Table 1). The mean age of the household was 35.98, education of participants were Illiterate 21 (7.63%), secondary school 126 (45.81%), High school 52(18.90%), Graduate 76 (27.63%). Employment of participants was Unemployed 236(85.81%), Govt. Employee 19(6.90), and Self Employed 14 (5.09%). The participants living with different size of family (on the basis of number of individuals are present in family) having Individuals 2-3 was 64 (23.27%), family of 4-6 individuals was 91 (33.09) and family with 5+ individuals was 120 (43.63.) The number of participants with 5+ years of experience in meal preparation was greater, at 127 (46.18%), among others.

Table1: Participants' socio-economic characteristics.

Variables	n=275	%	p-Value
Age	18-29	69	25.09
	30-45	97	35.27
	46-55	109	39.63
Education	Illiterate	21	7.63
	Secondary School	126	45.81
	High School	52	18.90
	Graduate	76	27.63
Employment	Unemployed	236	85.81
	Prefer not to answer	6	2.18
	Govt. Employee	19	6.90
	Self employed	14	5.09

Size of family	2-3	64	23.27	0.000
	4-6	91	33.09	
	6+	120	43.63	
Experience in preparing meals (yrs)	Less than 1	32	11.63	0.003
	1-3	49	17.18	
	3-5	67	24.36	
	5+	127	46.18	

Table2: Assessment of the knowledge of hygiene in participants before and after the Covid19 pandemic n=275

Variable		Before Covid19	%	After Covid19	%	p-value
Hand hygiene and proper hand washing	Secure	17	6.18	210	76.36	0.3
	Mild	10	3.63	26	9.45	
	Primary	52	18.90	36	13.09	
	No Knowledge	196	71.27	3	1.09	
Cleaning groceries	Secure	5	1.81	167	60.72	0.02
	Mild	25	9.09	39	14.18	
	Primary	156	56.72	26	9.45	
	No Knowledge	89	32.36	40	14.54	
Food security Knowledge	Secure	52	18.90	179	65.09	0.08
	Mild	52	18.90	56	20.36	
	Primary	93	33.18	35	12.72	
	No Knowledge	78	28.36	5	1.81	
Expenditure on hygiene	Per month (INR)	300/-		1500/-		
Use of Hand sanitizer	Secure	9	3.27	245	89.09	0.022
	Mild	39	14.18	10	3.63	
	Primary	164	59.63	18	3.63	
	No Knowledge	63	22.90	2	0.72	
Hygiene while using kitchen utensils.	Secure	68	24.72	213	77.45	0.014
	Mild	10	3.63	25	9.09	
	Primary	197	71.63	37	13.45	
	No Knowledge	0	0	0	0	

In our study, the most significant difference was observed in kitchen and food hygiene in terms of sanitization for infection prevention. The expenditure on the hygiene was increased fivefold. We selected higher levels of observed data to summarize Table 2. Hand hygiene and proper hand washing knowledge in participants before Covid19 was in the category "No knowledge" with 196 (71.27%), but Secure knowledge was 210 (73.36%) after Covid19.

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Discussion

The aim of this study was to assess the hygiene impact of the COVID-19 pre and post emergence, on households in Jagdalpur, India. As a result, a questionnaire was used to collect information on household expenses, also knowledge of food security, hand hygiene and proper hand washing, the usage of hand sanitizer, and hygiene when using kitchen utensils before and after the COVID-19 pandemic. Food safety is receiving heightened consideration worldwide as one of the essential links between food and health [17].

Policymakers should offer food safety education initiatives to food insecure families in order to lower the risk of foodborne disease. In an integrated global economy, the COVID-19 pandemic has a worldwide impact on people, households, and society as a whole.

Limitations

The study was carried out in an area of Jagdalpur where the bulk of the population is not exposed to such surveys. Difficulties were identified in gathering accurate responses from individuals rather than actual-life data.

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Conflicts of interest: All authors declared no personal or financial conflicts of interest.

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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